

How Does The Shape And Configuration Affect A Spacecraft When It Is Re-entering The Atmosphere?

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ABSTRACT

In the first section, there will be explanations on the different types of shapes and configurations of current spacecraft, and why they are built that way. In the second section, there are challenges that aerospace engineers need to overcome in order to build a spacecraft that can re-enter the atmosphere safely. The third section will go into specific factors that will influence re-entry, depending on the speed of the vehicle and the configuration of the spacecraft itself. After that, this research paper will explain areas of improvement and future designs in section 4. Finally, there will be a summary regarding the findings in the research paper, why it is important to continue researching/developing re-entry vehicles, and how these findings will contribute to the aerospace community.

Keywords: Strakes, Aerodynamic Heating, Speed Regimes, Peak Heat flux, Fluid Flows

Glossary:

Strakes-small fins located on the body of a spacecraft that aid in flow of fluids during re-entry and landing corrections.

Aerodynamic Heating-the heating of a spacecraft as it travels quickly through the atmosphere, converting its kinetic energy into heat energy.

Speed Regimes-the different speeds a spacecraft is traveling in the atmosphere, ranging from low to high or from subsonic to hypersonic.

Fluid Flows-a term used to describe the motion and the flow of a fluid.

Peak Heat flux-The maximum heat transfer in the heat between a spacecraft and the atmosphere it is traveling through.

1. INTRODUCTION

This research was conducted in order for aerospace engineers to understand several factors they have to consider when designing a new spacecraft. This is essential because during the re-entry process, there are several factors engineers have to consider in making their design, such as the ability to tolerate aerodynamic heating, speed regimes, and g-force influencing the spacecraft. Understanding these contributing factors, effects under different conditions, and solutions such as structural designs, materials, and mechanisms would allow researchers to determine how their spacecraft should be designed.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research paper was conducted by researching different models of rockets and capsules in order to identify similarities, and differences in their design. It includes researching various mechanisms present on various spacecraft, and how their structure, materials, and method of re-entry allow safe re-entry traveling through the atmosphere.

In addition, the different factors of re-entry are also addressed by conducting online research. Topics such as aerodynamic heating, peak heat flux, speed regimes, etc are researched while making the connections to designing rockets and capsule systems.

This research paper utilizes research designs that are descriptive, correlation, and exploratory. A descriptive research design was conducted to describe the structural and mechanical analysis of various rocket designs. In addition, it was used to address the fluid dynamics of heat

transfer/aerodynamic heating during re-entry. Next, a correlation research design is used in order to make the connections between different challenges comforted during re-entry and reasons for designs of various spacecraft models. Finally, the research paper uses an exploratory research paper analysis by explaining the reason various spacecraft models are designed the way they were. In addition, it was used to address how we can come up with more effective solutions, like combining elements of the Space Shuttle and the SpaceX capsule in order to bridge the conflict of spacecraft design.

3. DISCUSSION

Current designs

Each spacecraft designed by SpaceX, Blue Origin, and the capsule from the Apollo mission each have different roles, but they are similar in design when it comes to re-entry.

Nasa Apollo Mission Capsule

(McGregor, n.d.).

The Apollo 10 mission was a mission that was planned by NASA to launch the fourth crewed flight to the moon. The capsule features a Command and Service Module (CSM) to keep the capsule in orbit around the moon, and a Lunar Module (LM) that was used to descend to/ascend from the moon. The Apollo 10 mission also includes a Command Module 106, Service Module 106, Lunar Module 4, a Spacecraft Lunar module Adapter, and a Launch Escape System to use in case of an emergency (Apollo 10 Complete Guide, n.d.). The capsule solves re-entry problems in terms of aerodynamic heating, center of gravity/pressure, speed regimes, and peak heat flux by using ablative materials for the heat shield, a blunt body design, and making sure the capsule is rotationally symmetrical. Using a shallow re-entry angle, the capsule limits aerodynamic heating further by limiting the time it experiences the most amount of heat. In addition, it spreads heat across the blunt body design, allowing oblique shock waves to occur more naturally during the re-entry phase.

Nasa Space Shuttle

(ESA, 2024).

(NASA, n.d.).

The NASA Space Shuttle was a design by NASA to create the first re-entry space vehicle that operates as a rocket during flight, and ascends like an airplane during the re-entry phase. One example is the orbiter, which was a transportation vehicle featuring a pressurized crew compartment, flight deck, middeck, airlock mid fuselage, and an AFT fuselage used to maneuver the spacecraft during re-entry (NASA-The Space Shuttle, 2023). As a lifting body, the space shuttle cannot be launched under its own power. In other words, it becomes a high tech glider, one that relies on additional aircrafts or rocket engines to create lift. The shuttle solves center of gravity and pressure by maintaining balance in front and rear of the vehicle, as well as the sides. In addition, the orbiter has a double delta wing configuration used to make flight efficient during hypersonic speeds, and providing a good lift to drag ratio when landing. For that reason, the space shuttle resolves flow regimes. Moreover, the shuttle solves peak heat flux by using a vertical stabilizer that has a rudder controlling the direction of the yaw (nose left and nose right). In this case, the split rudder on the space shuttle orbiter works both as a rudder and as a speed brake during atmospheric re-entry.

In addition, this deflects the airflow, increases drag and decreases the orbiter's speed as it rolls along the runway upon landing. Furthermore, the space shuttle is equipped with two different types of engines, OMS (orbital maneuvering system) and RCS (reaction control engines) that are

used to propel the space shuttle to outer space, change its orbit, docking at a space station, and deorbit for re-entry and into the earth's atmosphere. These two engines are important in terms of overcoming peak heat flux by preventing the space shuttle from entering the atmosphere too quickly (NASA- The Aeronautics of the Space Shuttle, n.d.).

Blue Origin New Shepard

(Blue Origin, n.d.).

The Blue Origin Space Capsule is a commercial space vehicle that was designed to carry untrained civilians into space. In addition, it was designed so that the capsule, the parachute, and the rockets can be reused many times. The capsule has a biconic cone and a blunt body design to

increase the landing accuracy and to orient the capsule horizontally during re-entry. As a biconic blunt body design, the capsule overcomes problems ranging from center of gravity, pressure, aerodynamic heating, fluid flows, and peak heat flux. The center of gravity and pressure can be solved accordingly by maintaining the shape and configuration to make the weight, and size of the vehicle proportional on all sides. In addition, the capsule addresses aerodynamic heating, and fluid flows by maintaining a smooth surface and rounded tip to distribute air flow around the capsule consistently. Finally, the peak heat flux can also be considered by using a conductive heat shield and a thermal protection system to manage the maximum amount of heat experienced during re-entry.

Space X Dragon Capsule

(SpaceX, n.d.).

The SpaceX Dragon is composed of the capsule to carry crew and pressurized cargo, as well as the trunk that carries unpressurized service modules. In the capsule, there is the service section and the nose cone, which opens during orbit and closes during the re-entry phase. The SpaceX Dragon Capsule is powered by Draco thrusters which provide orbital aligning during flight. Besides that, the capsule also includes a solar array, and a radiator that prevents overheating

(Rauf, 2023). When it comes down to the capsule's design, it addresses the center of gravity, pressure, aerodynamic heating, fluid flow, and peak heat flux. Specifically, the capsule solves the center of gravity and pressure by keeping the shape and weight of the structure equivalent on each side. In addition, it solves aerodynamic heating and peak heat flux through a blunt body design. Combined with a shallow re-entry angle, a biconic blunt body design allows oblique shockwaves to deflect heat away from the spacecraft, and increase the landing accuracy. What's more, the combination of a blunt body design and a biconic rounded cone allows air flow to be constant across the body of the capsule.

Space X Falcon 9

(SpaceX, n.d.).

The SpaceX falcon 9 is a type of rocket developed by Space X to accommodate and send cargo to space. It is powered by nine Merlin engines that provide an initial thrust of 125,000 pounds of thrust. The second stage of the falcon 9 rocket is powered by one Merlin engine providing the same thrust. On certain missions, the falcon 9 has a Dragon Capsule on the tip of the second stage to carry astronauts and cargo to the International Space Station (Lethbridge, n.d.). In order to address factors such as the center of gravity, pressure, aerodynamic heating, peak heat flux, and fluid flows, a few features are added to the rocket.

Specifically, to maintain the center of gravity and pressure, the Falcon 9 balances the first stage and second stage of the rocket booster before and after the separation. To address aerodynamic heating and fluid flows, the capsule is designed to be rotationally symmetric. In addition, grid fins can address aerodynamic heating by slowing down the Falcon 9 rocket during the descent gradually. In other words, combined with Merlin engines that fire in retro-grade (providing thrust opposite of the spacecraft's motion) and grid fins, the spacecraft is able to successfully land back onto the landing platform.

Space X Starship

(Etherington, n.d.).

Starship is positioned on top of a rocket booster named Super Heavy. During re-entry, Starship flips on its side to maximize the amount of air resistance hitting the spacecraft, slowing it down. Once the spaceship is in position it will reignite its engines and flip itself back into a vertical position before docking. Through several factors, the SpaceX Starship is able to address the center of gravity, pressure, aerodynamic heating, speed regimes, fluid flows, and peak heat flux. In this case, Starship solves the center of gravity and pressure by using a bilateral symmetry to maintain the weight and shape of the spacecraft. The reason why Starship have wings is to aid in

controlled descent and to slow down as it nears the platform. Specifically, these wings are capable of controlling pitch, attitude, and roll while descending. In order to solve aerodynamic heating, speed regimes, and peak heat flux, the spacecraft uses a blunt body design to create oblique shockwaves in the atmosphere to help disperse heat during the re-entry phase. Lastly, Starship solves fluid flow by making the surface of the ship smooth to maintain air flow.

Findings: features of spacecrafts during re-entry phase

Blunt rocket design-the Nasa Apollo 10 mission capsule, Space Shuttle, and the Starship all feature blunt rocket design. A wider body means that a starship is able to capture higher drag at higher altitudes, slowing the spacecraft, lowering the g force, and directing the flow of aerodynamic heating. The main advantage of having a blunt body design over other rocket designs is the ability to produce normal **shockwaves**, allowing heat to be transferred proportionally across the spacecraft. **Shockwaves** are created when objects are moving Mach 1 (the speed of sound) and above. During this time, the object is traveling so quickly that air molecules are compressed in front of the object. As a result, this compression causes aerodynamic heating and build up pressure.

Biconic rocket design-the Blue Origin capsule and the SpaceX Dragon Crew both have a **biconic shape capsule**, allowing the spacecraft to be oriented vertically for launch and horizontally for re-entry (Blue Origin completes system requirements for innovative space vehicle, 2012). The main advantage of this shape is to limit the landing area to reduce recovery time (ESA Acrv, n.d.).

Grid Fins-Another advantage that spacex rockets have are **grid fins** that are used to orient the spacecraft in the right way during landing. Specifically, these fins are placed in an x-wing configuration where the air bounces off the fins to generate drag force and slow the rocket during the descent. They are strong enough to resist the **hypersonic flow**, air with speeds exceeding Mach 5 (Grid Fins & Rocket Guidance). As a result, shockwaves are generated through these fins at and above mach 1 and above (Grid Fins & Rocket Guidance). As a result, a grid fin is used ideally when the spacecraft is slowing down during low supersonic speed, allowing the booster to activate and landing the spacecraft.

(SpaceX, n.d.).

Strakes-the purpose of having strakes is for gliding and generating lift for the spacecraft. During re-entry, strakes can be used to increase the landing accuracy of a spacecraft and allow it to have better control over the flow of air. These features are present on the blue origin capsule.

Shallow reentry angles are angles used by re-entry capsules to limit g-force and to create a low maximum heating rate for a long period of time. For that reason, it creates a trade off where the spacecraft experiences more heating due to low maximum heating. (FAA-Returning from Space: Re-entry, n.d.).

(Exo Cruiser, n.d.).

Gimbaling Mechanism is another feature used by rockets to align the spacecraft either during launch, re-entry, or while landing at the site. Gimbals are essential if a spacecraft needs to launch into a specific region of space or land in a specific designated area.

Double delta wing configuration is a feature used by the space shuttle to gain better control descent during re-entry. Using these wings will allow the spacecraft to gain lift and decrease the re-entry speed.

Current Designs and Considerations

Therefore, current spacecrafts have the ability to make a space journey safe and efficient. This is the case since engineers have invested their time and efforts to consider the shape and heat distribution of a spacecraft, the type of mechanics that is used (ex. Gimbal, retro-rockets, grid fins, and aft fins) which allow the spacecraft to re-enter the atmosphere safely and land in a designated area. While that is the case, engineers still have to invest more of their time to make sure that every system is cooperating efficiently, and to limit the amount of aerodynamic heating that is damaging the materials used during the re-entry phase.

One other consideration that aerospace engineers can consider is combining both elements of a space shuttle glide and descent control with a space capsule's ability to overcome aerodynamic heating. The details will be discussed more in future uses.

Challenges and Considerations/Background Knowledge

During re-entry, a spacecraft will have to consider the **center of gravity (the rotation of the rocket relative to the center of a body of mass, where the weight is equally distributed)**. During re-entry, the center of gravity will remain constant. (Rocket Center of Gravity, n.d). In addition, there is the **center of pressure** which is the average location of the pressure when the angle of attack is either increased or decreased. The center of pressure is influenced by lift and drag, and is a point on a rocket where air pressure is concentrated (Rocket Center of pressure, n.d.). One thing to keep in mind is that air pressure can change at different parts of the atmosphere. For instance, lower altitudes have more concentration of air molecules, contributing to increased airflow flowing around the rocket. The rockets and capsule mentioned in the previous section are examples where the center of gravity, as well as the center of pressure have been taken into consideration during the design process.

Moreover, aerospace engineers will have to take into consideration **aerodynamic heating**, which is the flow of gasses over a spacecraft that causes an additional heat load through the system. During re-entry, aerodynamic heating is mainly caused by the high velocity during re-entry. During these high speeds, the spacecraft's kinetic energy is transferred into thermal energy when passing by air molecules at a high velocity. As a result, rockets with blunt body design can limit aerodynamic heating due to their ability to disperse heat through shockwaves. This occurs when the blunt cone design converts kinetic energy into internal energy, heating the gas to cause dissociation and ionization. As a result, most of the energy is transferred into the spacecraft's wake rather than being on the surface. Therefore, the more blunt a rocket becomes, the higher the shockwave by providing a higher protective effect (NASA-Stagnation Point Heating, n.d.).

(Thompson, Haskins, n.d.).

This image shows how temperatures increase towards the center of the capsule where all the air molecules are concentrated. As a result, a material and design that can spread out heat evenly is needed. One option is **conductive materials** like copper and nickel, which can spread heat evenly across a surface. Another material that can be used are **ablative materials**, which absorb the heat through chemical reaction and break down during re-entry. As a result, they differ from conductive materials because they absorb the heat and need to be reapplied for each mission. One option is to use these two types of heatshields during re-entry. As a double layer heat shield, utilizing both materials will make sure that in case one heat shield is compromised during a mission, another heatshield can take its place during re-entry. However, one heat shield might be more important for one mission, so the type of heat shield will depend on the location, size, and purpose of the spacecraft.

To add on, one other factor that aerospace engineers have to consider is the weight of the spacecraft. This is the case because as the weight of the vehicle increases, it is more difficult to slow down the capsule due to a higher inertia. For instance, if there are two capsules of different masses travel at the same speed during re-entry, then the capsule with the higher mass will take

more energy to slow down because it has a higher inertia while the smaller capsule requires less energy because it has a lower inertia. Therefore, it is important to keep a balance between the material and the weight of the spacecraft.

There are several **speed regimes** in total with different properties. These range from Subsonic, Transonic, Supersonic, High Supersonic, and Hypersonic where speeds can be lower than mach 1 or as high as mach 5-10 (Sia, 2021). In this case, Hypersonic is the most difficult speed regime to travel through since it has a higher temperature and pressure acting upon the spacecraft. Traveling at Mach 10 and more during re-entry, most spacecraft designs need to take into consideration higher temperature/pressure.

In addition, aerospace engineers need to factor in **shockwaves**. Specifically, there are two types of shockwaves, **Oblique** and **Normal**. Both shockwaves form when an object is moving faster than the speed of sound. However they are different since Oblique shockwaves are formed in the direction of gases while a normal shockwave forms perpendicular to the flow direction, When a gas forms perpendicular to the flow direction, it means that the motion of the shockwave is facing the motion of the gas passing over the spacecraft. Due to this, normal shockwaves create a higher temperature as the gasses are compressed. Once it is compressed, the gas's temperature will rise significantly, leading to an increase in temperature on the spacecraft. As an energy conversion, kinetic energy during re-entry is converted into internal energy in the form of heat.

As a result, **Oblique shockwaves** are better for re-entry due to the lower heat transfer. This is the case since it takes longer time for the gas compression to occur, which reduces the sudden thermal load acting on the spacecraft. In addition, it allows for better energy dissipation since the energy in an oblique shock wave occurs further from the spacecraft, allowing less heat to reach the surface. Finally, oblique shockwaves also reduces the overall pressure drag, which allows the spacecraft to handle deceleration better by reducing structural damage during re-entry. This is done since oblique shockwaves occurred in a direction along the fluid flow (Nasa-Oblique Shock Wave, n.d.).

Looking closer, we can see different types of **fluid flows** acting on a capsule during re-entry. These include **Laminar, Turbulent, and Transitional**. A Laminar flow is a type of flow where air flows are smooth and parallel to one another. Just like how water flows through a hose, the

flow, velocity, and pressure is constant through a laminar flow during atmospheric re-entry. As the fluid layer divides into different layers, the fluid will stay parallel to one another. On the other hand, a turbulent flow is where the flow of fluid is irregular and can be difficult to predict. Unlike laminar flow, the flow of fluid will not be parallel to one another, can intersect one another, and be in unpredictable motions. Lastly, there is transitional flow, which is a type of flow having characteristics of Laminar and Turbulent flows. In fact, it is between these two types of fluid flows and has both smooth and irregular flows (Types of Fluid Flows, n.d.). When designing a spacecraft, we need to limit aerodynamic heating to **Laminar** flow. This is the case since Laminar flows not only create small frictional forces, but it also lowers the surface temperature of the spacecraft and makes the fluid predictable and easier to control.

One way we can keep the fluid flow during atmospheric re-entry to Laminar flow is through the **Reynold's number**, which is a type of calculation used to measure the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces. Viscous forces, in simple terms, is the sliding friction force between two solid surfaces. On this occasion, it is ideal that we keep the Reynold's number less than 2100 to indicate laminar flow, and greater than 2100 to achieve turbulent flow (Internal Edition University Physics, 1984). In order to produce a **laminar** flow, we need to limit the value of density, velocity, and the length of the heat shield to a limited value. Shown below is the formula for the Reynold number to keep the density, velocity, and the length of the material at a certain range to make sure that the value is smaller than 2100. In the simplified version, we only have to keep the velocity of the spacecraft and the length of the heat shield minimal in order to obtain the same effect. See the below diagram for more details.

$$Re = \frac{\rho \cdot V \cdot L}{\mu} \text{ or } Re = \frac{V \cdot L}{\nu}$$

Re = Reynolds number

ρ = Density

V = Velocity

L = Length

μ = Bulk viscosity

ν = Kinematic viscosity

One other factor aerospace engineers have to consider is **peak heat flux**, which is the maximum rate of heat transfer that is going on between the heat in the atmosphere and the spacecraft. In peak heat flux, there are **heat load, peak deceleration, and peak dynamic pressure**. First, we have heat load, or the maximum amount of temperature that can be added to a system. Next is peak deceleration, or the rate at which a spacecraft slows down during re-entry. Finally, there is peak dynamic pressure, or the movement of gasses over a spacecraft. (Nasa-Dynamic Pressure, n.d.). Specifically, it relates to the type of fluid flows mentioned above because it shows that fluid flows need to be laminar to maintain the surface temperature of the heatshield.

Mentioned in the earlier section was re-entry angles. There are three types of re-entry methods: **shallow, steep, and ballistic**. A **shallow re-entry angle** is where a spacecraft enters the atmosphere at a slanted angle, limiting the g-force and allowing for a low maximum heating rate for a longer time. On the other hand, a **steep re-entry angle** is where a spacecraft enters the atmosphere quicker at a steeper angle, causing more g-force, and having a higher maximum heating rate for a short time. Lastly, there are **ballistic reentry angles** where a capsule rolls along its center like a barrel through rotational circular motion. This influences a spacecraft because it allows it to descend into the atmosphere quicker (FAA-Returning from Space Re-entry, n.d.). When re-entering, a spacecraft should incorporate a shallow re-entry angle since it creates more aerodynamic drag on the spacecraft, allowing it to have a slower descent speed. In other words, although it doesn't limit the aerodynamic heating significantly, it ensures that the spacecraft and the crew withstand a lower gravitational force. Shown below is a chart comparing

the total heat load in relation to the re-entry velocity, showing the difference between re-entry speeds between shallow, steep, and ballistic reentry angles.

(FAA-Returning from Space Re-entry, n.d.).

Toward the end, the important factors that aerospace engineers need to consider are **center of gravity, center of pressure, aerodynamic heating, flow regimes, and the peak dynamic pressure, deceleration, and the heat load.** In addition, engineers have to take into account limiting **Reynold’s number to 2100** or lower. This is important because as we are transitioning or improving existing spacecraft designs, we need to consider how factors during re-entry will change in relation to the changes on the design. Moreover, the center of gravity and pressure indicates that there is a balance between the upper and lower portions of a spacecraft. These features are evident on the SpaceX rockets, Nasa Apollo Missions, New Shepard Capsules, and the Dragon Crew Mission Capsule. In terms of aerodynamic heating, it demonstrates how space vehicles such as the SpaceX Starship and the NASA Space Shuttle have a blunt body design. Using a blunt body design allows heat to be deflected away through oblique shockwaves (NASA-Oblique Shockwave, n.d.). In addition, it describes how SpaceX starships and the Falcon 9 have grid fins incorporated in their design. Using Grid Fins specifically allows a spacecraft to slow down during the descent, limiting the amount of aerodynamic heating on the surface of the heatshield. In another case, aerodynamic heating and flow regimes illustrate why capsules use

shallow reentry angles when entering the atmosphere. Examples of this are present on the NASA Apollo Mission Capsule, Blue Origin, and the Dragon Crew Capsule. Finally, peak dynamic pressure and deceleration contributes to gimbaling mechanism and grid fins designs. Specifically, these incorporations are seen on SpaceX rockets where their purpose is to slow and decelerate the spacecraft down during descent.

Future uses

When it comes to new designs, there are a few things that need to be incorporated. For instance, an engineer needs to take into consideration either using only a blunt, biconic design, or elements from both designs. To recap, a blunt body design can be used to create oblique shockwaves that deflect heat away from the spacecraft. This type of shockwaves occur when the capsule is traveling at supersonic speeds. With shallow reentry angles, oblique shockwaves are more likely to occur. On the other hand, a biconic cone can be used to increase the landing accuracy. By combining elements from biconic cones and a blunt body design, a spacecraft can decrease aerodynamic heating while increasing the landing accuracy significantly. These features are already present on the Apollo Mission Capsule, SpaceX Dragon Crew, New Shepard Capsule, making them blunt body biconic spacecrafts. In addition, we can use grid fins, and strakes to improve the efficiency of a spacecraft during re-entry. In this case, spacecraft relying on landing accuracy may also incorporate grid fins and gimbaling mechanisms, reducing the complexity and cost of manufacturing.

In terms of aerodynamics and dynamic fluid, it is important to keep Reynold's number below 2100 to create a laminar flow. In addition the density, velocity, and the length of the capsule needs to be taken into consideration. Peak Deceleration, Dynamic Pressure, and the Heat Load can be determined through simulations to find the rate of descent, pressure, and the maximum heat exchange a spacecraft can withstand. Equally important, we need to consider the center of pressure and gravity when designing a new rocket or capsule during the re-entry process. This is essential because during a mission, a rocket can have new features, but it still needs to be balanced in terms of pressure and gravity acting upon the spacecraft.

As demonstrated in the previous section, a spacecraft should re-entry through shallow reentry angles, which allows for a slower velocity and a wider descent angle. By doing so, the spacecraft

limits the amount of aerodynamic heating that is acting on the heat shield, g-force, and acceleration by limiting the pressure during re-entry. On the other hand, a spacecraft should not enter through steep or ballistic reentry because it will lead to a faster descent speed and a higher g-force acting upon the spacecraft. In other words, as the speed of the spacecraft increases during atmospheric re-entry, there is more heating since the vehicle is traveling through the atmosphere quicker.

To add on, engineers in future development might need to consider using conductive or ablative materials for the heat shield depending on the mission. Ablative materials can be safer for a mission because it overcomes aerodynamic heating by absorbing the heat on the surface of the spacecraft. On the other hand, a conductive material might be used for smaller missions where the re-entry speed might be lower, allowing the heat to spread evenly across the surface. While that could be the case, combining both elements might be a good idea to ensure that in case one heat shield does not work during re-entry, there is another heat shield that can complete the job. However, using both heat shields will increase the weight of a spacecraft, so the combination depends on the purpose and payload of a mission.

One other option we can develop re-entry spacecraft is to use a hybrid design that incorporates both the Space Shuttle and the capsule designs like the SpaceX Dragon. In this case, the capsule will still have a blunt body design to generate oblique shockwaves, either conductive or ablative heat shields, and escape mechanism in case something went wrong. In addition, the crew compartment should have good insulation to protect the crew during aerodynamic heating. Here, double delta wings can be incorporated to provide better controlled gliding during re-entry. As the concentration of air molecules increases with decreasing atmosphere levels, the spacecraft will be able to get a better control over the re-entry speed. In order to minimize air resistance and to maximize the launch efficiency of the spacecraft, the double delta wings must be folded or retracted to prevent increasing drag during launch and the early phase of re-entry. However, doing so can increase the weight of the spacecraft, so it is important to design a light weighted mechanism for the foldable wings while making sure the weight is consistent. By combining both elements into a hybrid design, this not only allows for better control over descent, but it also increases the payload capacity while maintaining the shape and configuration of a normal capsule.

4. CONCLUSION

To conclude, this research paper went over different types of spacecraft designs and their advantage in terms of re-entry. There were topics ranging from SpaceX rockets, New Shepard from Blue Origin, and previous capsules developed by NASA Apollo missions. In addition, this research went over specific factors that aerospace engineers need to take into consideration when designing a spacecraft. This includes topics ranging from center of gravity, center of pressure, speed regimes, fluid regimes, aerodynamic heating, and peak deceleration/dynamic pressure/heat load. Finally, the paper ends with future applications for spacecraft including the most important factors that engineers need to take into consideration.

Although there exist current spacecraft that meet the safety and standards in terms of re-entry, further development in terms of aerodynamic heating, peak deceleration, dynamic pressure and heat load needs to be considered. This is the case since spacecrafts still suffer from the impacts of aerodynamic heating that is wearing the heat shield, complete distribution of heat across a surface, and factoring in the flow of fluid at different times during the re-entry phase. While this can be the case, this research paper will let aerospace engineers understand the most important factors they need to consider during the re-entry phase, and how to balance out different features added without compromising the capabilities of a spacecraft and its performance during launch and re-entry. In addition, this research paper will give engineers insight into changes that need to be made during the development phase in order to ensure a safe and efficient mission.

5. LIMITATIONS

While this research paper goes into details the shape and configurations of a spacecraft, it only addresses the main designs of each individual spacecraft during re-entry. In other words, it does not necessarily address all of the design and technical applications there may be.

6. REFERENCES

Apollo 11 Space. (2024, May 18). *Apollo 10 complete guide*. Apollo 11 Space. <https://apollo11space.com/apollo-10-complete-guide/>

Arfken, G. B., Griffing, D. F., Kelly, D. C., & Priest, J. (1984). FLUID MECHANICS. In *Elsevier eBooks* (pp. 306–325). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-059858-8.50021-2>

Bandivadekar, D. (2020, August 10). *Conquering the fast and the furious: Physics of atmospheric re-entry*. theGIST. <https://the-gist.org/2020/07/conquering-the-fast-and-the-furious-physics-of-atmospheric-re-entry/>

Beck, A. S. (2017). *Thermal Protection System Fundamentals* [Slide show]. Thermal and Fluid Analysis Workshop, Huntsville, Alabama, United States of America. Nasa. <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20170011453/downloads/20170011453.pdf>

Blue Origin. (2023, January 3). *Blue Origin Completes System Requirements Review for innovative space vehicle* | Blue Origin. <https://www.blueorigin.com/news/blue-origin-completes-system-requirements-review-for-innovative-space-vehicle>

Blue Origin. (2024, May 8). *New Shepard* | Blue Origin. <https://www.blueorigin.com/new-shepard>

Brahmbhatt, R. (2023, April 20). Why SpaceX's Starship mega-rocket looks unlike anything the company has ever built before. *Business Insider*. <https://www.businessinsider.com/why-spacex-starship-is-black-and-silver-2023-3#:~:text=Stainless%20steel%20on%20the%20other,stainless%20steel%20to%20prevent%20corrosion.>

ESA ACRV. (n.d.). <http://www.astronautix.com/e/esaacrv.html>

Etherington, D. (2019, September 28). *SpaceX's Starship MK1 spacecraft prototype in pictures*. Tech Crunch. https://techcrunch.com/2019/09/28/gallery-spacexs-starship-mk1-spacecraft-prototype-in-pictures/?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuYmluZy5jb20v&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAAJ964WpSAycF20z8rJFFaFVpb1ohQYTwX45qfrxR92x-CQv_STIYSLGapopKP3JevltmHuBdPWK7capbSFyy2tBAdhIvO1KQxgkC1CZvK-3LGrbCJ1vNyVvs8gCbFRLhQgnL4jPq9Ud1M8SDVgTpVvmksDtKw05ewZDIJa5CvGNV

FALCON 9 FACT SHEET | *Spaceline*. (n.d.). <https://www.spaceline.org/cape-canaveral-rocket-missile-program/falcon-9-fact-sheet/#:~:text=The%20pressurized%20Dragon%20capsule%20measures%2023.6%20feet%20high,cargo%20and%20astronauts%20to%20the%20International%20Space%20Station>.

From pennies to propulsion: The use of Copper in aerospace. (2023b, August 15). <https://www.ursamajor.com/blog/from-pennies-to-propulsion-the-use-of-copper-in-aerospace>

Grid Fins & Rocket guidance. (n.d.). <https://www.spaceandscience.fr/en/blog/grid-fins>

Guo, B., & Ghalambor, A. (2005). Transportation. In *Elsevier eBooks* (pp. 219–262). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-1-933762-41-8.50018-6>

Hitchings, L. (2020, February 19). SpaceX unveils sleek, reusable Dragon crew capsule. *New Scientist*. <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn25652-spacex-unveils-sleek-reusable-dragon-crew-capsule/>

Kremer, K. (2015, December 24). *SpaceX Falcon 9 set for critical engine test firing on Monday, April 30 - Universe Today*. Universe Today. <https://www.universetoday.com/94626/spacex-falcon-9-set-for-critical-engine-test-firing-on-monday-april-30/>

Malik, T. (2019, March 22). SpaceX's Hexagon Tiles for Starship Heat Shield Pass Fiery Test. *Space.com*. <https://www.space.com/spacex-starship-hexagon-heat-shield-tile-test.html>

Morse, M. D. (1996). Supersonic beam sources. In *Experimental methods in the physical sciences* (pp. 21–47). [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0076-695x\(08\)60784-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0076-695x(08)60784-x)

NASA Glenn Research Center. (2024, April 4). *Dynamic pressure | Glenn Research Center | NASA*. <https://www1.grc.nasa.gov/beginners-guide-to-aeronautics/dynamic-pressure-2/>

NASA@SC23: Simulating Capsule Free-Flight for planetary entry, descent, and landing. (n.d.). <https://www.nas.nasa.gov/SC23/research/project15.html>

NASA. (2024, June 3). *The Space Shuttle - NASA*. <https://www.nasa.gov/reference/the-space-shuttle/>

NASA. (2023, July 26). The Aeronautics of the Space Shuttle - NASA. *NASA*. <https://www.nasa.gov/centers-and-facilities/langley/the-aeronautics-of-the-space-shuttle/#:~:text=The%20space%20shuttle%2C%20with%20a,is%20a%20high%2Dtech%20glider.>

Oblique shock waves. (n.d.). <https://www.grc.nasa.gov/WWW/k-12/airplane/oblique.html>

Rajamani, A. (n.d.). Heat Shields for Re-Entry Vehicles-A Review. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology*, 12(3). <https://www.ijert.org/research/heat-shields-for-re-entry-vehicles-a-review-IJERTV12IS030106.pdf>

Rauf, J. (2023). Space X Dragon Spacecraft. In *University of California*. <https://www.uc.edu/content/dam/refresh/cont-ed-62/olli/fall-23-class-handouts/SpaceX%20Dragon%20Capsules.pdf>

Re-Entry aircraft. (n.d.).
<https://www.grc.nasa.gov/WWW/BGH/hihyper.html#:~:text=The%20Shuttle%20uses%20a%20rocket%20propulsion%20system%20to,altitudes%20above%2050%20miles%20makes%20aerodynamic%20surfaces%20ineffective.>

Returning from space: Re-entry. (n.d.). In the Federal *Aviation Agency*. FAA.
https://www.faa.gov/sites/faa.gov/files/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/avs/III.4.1.7_Returning_from_Space.pdf

Richard, I. (2021, November 24). Blue Origin NS-19 Mission Details New Passengers Including Alan Shepard's Daughter, GMA's Michael Strahan, and MORE. *Tech Times*.
<https://www.techtimes.com/articles/268420/20211123/blue-origin-ns-19-mission-details-new-passengers-including-alan.htm>

Roulette, J. (2022, February 11). *What is Starship?* New York Times.
<https://www.nytimes.com/article/elon-musk-starship.html>

Scott Manley. (2018, October 23). *Ballistic Reentry vs Aerodynamic Reentry* [Video]. YouTube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HgTNzDCc0gk>

Sia, J. (2023, March 25). *Rocket Physics, The Hard Way: Re-entry and hypersonic flight*. The Mars Society of Canada.
<https://www.marssociety.ca/2021/06/24/rocket-physics-the-hard-way-re-entry-and-hypersonic-flight/>

Staff, P. M. C. E. (n.d.). *How does the Reynolds number affect mixer design?*
<https://academy.paulmueller.com/how-does-the-reynolds-number-affect-mixer-design>

Stimac, V. (2023, July 24). Where to see the Apollo Command modules (Updated for 2023) ★
Space Tourism guide. Space Tourism Guide.
<https://spacetourismguide.com/apollo-command-modules/>

STS-9 landing. (n.d.). https://www.esa.int/ESA_Multimedia/Images/2024/01/STS-9_landing

The Differences Between Laminar vs. Turbulent Flow. (n.d.). System Analysis Blog | Cadence.
<https://resources.system-analysis.cadence.com/blog/msa2022-the-differences-between-laminar-vs-turbulent-flow>

Types of Fluid Flows. (2022, January 1). Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University.
<https://doi.org/10.15394/eaglepub.2022.1066.n11>

Vedantu. (n.d.). *Heat load Formula.* VEDANTU.
<https://www.vedantu.com/formula/heat-load-formula>

Stagnation point heating. (n.d.). *[Slide show].* NASA.
<https://tfaws.nasa.gov/TFAWS12/Proceedings/Aerothermodynamics%20Course.pdf>